

WHO'S WHO? NAVIGATING THE FCT R&I STAKEHOLDER ECOSYSTEM

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Acronyms

AISBL	International Non-Profit Association
ASD	Aerospace, Security and Defence Industries Association of Europe
CEPOL	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training
CERIS	Community for European Research and Innovation for Security
CL3	Cluster 3 (Civil Security for Society)
COSI	Standing Committee on Operational Cooperation on Internal Security
CoU	Community of Users
DG HOME	Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs
EACTDA	European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EC3	European Cybercrime Centre
ECTEG	European Cybercrime Training and Education Group
EIL	Europol Innovation Lab
ENLETS	European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services
EOS	European Organisation for Security
EU	European Union
EUCB	European Clearing Board for Innovation
EUDA	European Union Drugs Agency
eu-LISA	European Union Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems
EMCDDA	European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism
FR	Flash Report
H2020	Horizon 2020
IT	Information Technology
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
LEWP	Law Enforcement Working Party
NCP	National Contact Point
R&I	Research and Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SIA	Security Innovation Award(s)
SKB	Structured Knowledge Base
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SMI2G	Security Mission Information & Innovation Group
WP	Work Programme

Introduction

In an era of borderless threats, operational law enforcement **cooperation** is essential to combat organised crime and terrorism. The EU facilitates quicker, safer, and more structured law enforcement cooperation through targeted actions steered by internal security policies.¹ Extending such cooperation beyond the operational arena is only natural, since the capability-based approach for security promoted by the European institutions relies, among other things, on Research and Innovation.²

Cooperation is inherent to **EU-funded research**, since it serves as a primary tool for pooling resources, expertise, and diverse perspectives to foster breakthroughs that would not be possible through individual actions. The European Commission has stressed the importance of cooperation, in particular in the domain of security research, by creating mechanisms and channels to foster the synergetic use of knowledge and resources for the development of future civil security capabilities.

During the **TECNOSEC 2025** exhibition,³ ENACT sponsored a roundtable discussion where different entities leveraging R&I as a security capability-enabler explained how they harnessed cooperation to achieve their objectives. Representatives of **Europol EC3**, **EACTDA**, the **Spanish National Police**, and **Portuguese Judicial Police** showcased the importance of a structured and connected R&I community. They presented their cooperation-enabling channels, such as the EC3 Advisory Groups,⁴ the Tools4LEAs project of EACTDA⁵ or the Innovation Procurement challenges of the Spanish Police,⁶ and discussed the difficulties of coordinating within the complex FCT R&I landscape, highlighting the importance of harmonising efforts and integrating diverse viewpoints to avoid unnecessary duplication.

With the aim of facilitating a better understanding of all the forces intervening in the EU-funded FCT R&I ecosystem, this report presents some of the key entities involved and their role in the R&I cycle.

¹https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/law-enforcement-cooperation_en

²SWD (2021) 422 final

³<https://www.tecnosec.es/>

⁴<https://www.europol.europa.eu/about-europol/european-cybercrime-centre-ec3/ec3-partners>

⁵<https://www.tools4leas.eu/about.html>

⁶https://www.cdti.es/forense_licitacion

The Main Actors in EU Security R&I

To understand the dynamics of the EU-funded FCT R&I cycle, it is important to know what the different stages of programming and implementation are. From the initial consultations, through the different drafts, and until the final adoption and implementation of the Work Programmes, different stakeholders intervene and contribute with different roles.

For the sake of simplification, and in the context of the Horizon programming and implementation cycle, the following **roles** are considered:

- **Programming and implementation:** Entities with the formal mandate to draft and adopt *strategic plans* and *Work Programmes* outlining priorities, funding opportunities, and timelines; to carry out budgetary control and manage the project proposal evaluation process; to monitor project performance; and to evaluate the overall impact of the programme.
- **Contribution:** Entities with a mandate to support the Commission in the programming and implementation of programmes by providing subject matter expertise.
- **Advisory:** Entities without a formal mandate to contribute to programming, but which provide input, either on their own initiative or upon request by the Commission, based on their subject matter knowledge.
- **Participation:** Entities that are beneficiaries of EU funding under the Horizon Europe programme.

This report presents some of the key entities involved in the FCT domain and their respective roles.

Figure 1: H2020 Work Programme Preparation Lifecycle, Including External Consultations and Expert Contributions (Source: European Commission)

Figure 2: Key Entities and their Roles

Programming and Implementation

The following entities are among those that define the strategic direction and manage the implementation of Cluster 3 Work Programmes, particularly under the FCT destination.

Entity	Description
<p>European Commission DG HOME (Migration and Home Affairs)⁷</p>	<p>The European Commission acts as the central manager of Horizon Europe, defining strategic priorities, adopting Work Programmes, and handling budget implementation. It oversees implementation, monitors performance through evaluations, and manages international partnerships to achieve EU research, innovation, and green/digital policy goals. Key roles of the European Commission include Strategic Planning, Budgetary Control, Implementation & Monitoring and Policy Development. As the lead department for EU policy on internal security, migration, and border management, DG HOME is responsible for ensuring that security R&I aligns with EU security policy in the domain of FCT, addressing the capability needs and gaps for a more effective and efficient action against current and future security threats. The DG provides the strategic policy steer for the security research programme and manages the programming of the Security Research Work Programmes throughout the programming and implementation cycle.</p>
<p>Horizon Europe Cluster 3 Programme Committee^{8,9}</p>	<p>This committee is a vital bridge between the European Commission and Member States, ensuring national interests are reflected in EU funding. Composed of representatives from all EU Member States, the committee is responsible for formally approving the multi-annual Work Programmes. It ensures that the proposed research topics address concrete capability gaps identified by national security authorities and practitioners and contributes to the competitiveness of their research and technology ecosystems.</p> <p>In addition to this, the whole Horizon Europe programme has a National Contact Point (NCP) system established. The National Contact Points are support structures established by Member States and Associated Countries and recognised by the European Commission to help participants to access the different EU Programme opportunities. For Horizon Europe, there are 17 NCP different functions plus the NCP national coordinators network, giving support to participants across the different parts of the programme. The Commission also funds networks of NCPs to improve trans-national collaboration between NCPs in support to the programme and its beneficiaries. In the case of CL3, this network is project SEREN.¹⁰</p>
<p>European Research Executive Agency (REA)¹¹</p>	<p>REA is the primary executive arm tasked with the efficient management of EU research funding. It manages the entire lifecycle of calls for proposals under Horizon Europe Cluster 3 (Civil Security for Society).¹²</p> <p>This mainly includes organising and managing the evaluation of proposals by independent experts, the signing of grant agreements, and the monitoring of the technical and financial progress of the funded projects.</p>

⁷https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/innovation-and-security-research_en

⁸<https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/cluster-3>

⁹<https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/ncp-networks/cluster-3/find-your-ncp?country-type=MS&order=country>

¹⁰<https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/ncp-networks/cluster-3/about-seren5>

¹¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/cluster-3-civil-security-society_en

¹²Except for the ECCC destination, which is indirectly managed by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC)

Contribute

Operational agencies translate field experience into research requirements. Since the beginning of the Horizon Europe programme, these agencies do not participate as beneficiaries in EU-funded R&I projects, but they contribute actively to the programming of the calls, the evaluation of the proposals, the monitoring of the project implementation and the assessment of results.

Some of the operational agencies that contribute more actively to the programming and implementation of FCT research are the following:

Entity	Description
<p>Europol¹³</p>	<p>Europol serves as the EU's primary information hub for law enforcement, coordinating intelligence and providing analytical support to Member States in the fight against serious organised crime and terrorism. Its involvement in R&I is led by the Europol Innovation Lab (EIL), whose mission is to identify, promote, and develop practical, forward-thinking solutions that enhance operational work across Member States. Among other tasks, the EIL supports the drafting of the FCT Work Programme and the evaluation of Horizon Europe research projects with industry, academia, civil society, and law enforcement.</p>
<p>eu-LISA¹⁴</p>	<p>The European Union Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (eu-LISA) is tasked with the operational management of the EU's large-scale IT systems, which serve as the technological backbone for border management, asylum, and justice. The research and innovation function of the Agency addresses these needs in the core technological domains of relevance to eu-LISA and its stakeholders, that are defined and regularly updated by the research and innovation team. Among other tasks, the Agency's mandate includes contributing to the implementation of parts of the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation relevant to the systems operated by the Agency, many of which fall under Cluster 3.</p>
<p>CEPOL¹⁵</p>	<p>The European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training focuses on making Europe safer by professionalising law enforcement officials through standardized vocational training and learning. It acts as a hub that provides officials with the essential skills needed to stay ahead of evolving threats like cybercrime, money laundering, and terrorism. Through international cooperation projects and exchange programmes, CEPOL raises awareness of EU information-sharing systems and ensures that the latest research bulletins and training curricula reach the staff of police and customs services across Member States.</p>
<p>EUDA¹⁶</p>	<p>The European Union Drugs Agency (EUDA), formerly the EMCDDA, serves as the central source of drug-related expertise, providing data and analysis to support healthier and more secure policy responses in Europe. As part of the EUDA's expanded mandate, the agency contributes actively to the EU Framework Programmes for research and innovation and work on identifying knowledge gaps and research priorities in the drugs area in the EU.</p>

¹³<https://www.europol.europa.eu/how-we-work/innovation-lab>

¹⁴<https://www.eulisa.europa.eu/activities/research-and-innovation>

¹⁵<https://www.cepol.europa.eu/about>

¹⁶https://www.euda.europa.eu/activities/drug-related-research_en

Advise

EU-funded R&I programming relies largely on consultations with external experts, entities and networks which provide subject matter knowledge to the Commission services and advise on matters related to the programming and implementation of the Work Programmes.

Entity	Description
<p>CERIS¹⁷</p>	<p>The Community for European Research and Innovation for Security is the primary informal consultative body for DG HOME. Developed from the former Community of Users for Safe, Secure and Resilient Societies (CoU), the CERIS community gathers more than 1,500 registered stakeholders (policymakers, end-users, academia, industry and civil society) and regularly holds thematic events with the security research community. The objectives of CERIS are to analyse identified capability needs and gaps in the corresponding areas; identify solutions available to address the gaps; translate capability gaps and potential solutions into research needs; identify funding opportunities and synergies between different funding instruments; identify standardisation research-related needs; integrate the views of citizens.</p>
<p>EU Innovation Hub for Internal Security¹⁸</p>	<p>Hosted at Europol is a collaborative network designed to ensure coordination among actors such as justice, border security, and law enforcement agencies.¹⁹ It maps existing projects and identifies potential overlaps to increase synergies and pool resources among the European Commission and various EU agencies like Frontex, eu-LISA, and CEPOL. By serving as a testing ground for innovative practices and leading projects, the Hub promotes a responsible and unified culture of innovation across the EU security architecture.</p>
<p>European Clearing Board for Innovation (EuCB)</p>	<p>The EuCB is the main network of Law Enforcement Agencies for Innovation affairs which works to drive innovation efforts of police forces across Member States with the support of the Europol Innovation Lab (EIL). It brings together all LEAs from EU Member States, as well as those from the four Schengen-associated countries. The EuCB concentrates on hosting strategic and core groups, which are dedicated to, e.g., developing tools, methods, and innovative approaches to enhance operational and investigative support for LEAs.</p> <p>The EuCB and the EIL collaborate closely, sharing knowledge and, where appropriate, jointly managing multiple types of activities related with innovation within the Law Enforcement landscape. This cooperation ensures the provision of the necessary resources, commitment, and tools to support innovation uptake effectively.</p> <p>In addition, the EuCB has established several strategic groups that provide policy advice, and core groups of dedicated LEAs working together to develop operational solutions.</p>
<p>European Organisation for Security²⁰</p>	<p>Represents the interests of the European security industry and research community. Operating in 15 different countries, EOS Members provide security research, solutions and services across many security domains, and work to promote a competitive EU security market and civil security research through high-level advocacy.</p>

¹⁷https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security_en

¹⁸<https://www.europol.europa.eu/how-we-work/innovation-lab/eu-innovation-hub-for-internal-security>

¹⁹<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7829-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

²⁰<https://www.eos-eu.com/>

Entity	Description
<p>Aerospace, Security and Defence Industries Association of Europe²¹</p>	<p>ASD is the voice of the European aerospace, security and defence industries. It represents more than 4,000 companies across 21 European countries. ASD advocates common positions on behalf of EU industries and provides technical expertise to public institutions and its member companies.</p>
<p>European Association of Research and Technology Organisations²²</p>	<p>EARTO represents Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) to ensure that research outputs are ready for productization. Its Security Research Working Group focuses on technical feasibility and the industrialisation of security assets. The group is composed of more than 20 active experts. Its members are active in EU security research programmes, share information on their proposal efforts, establish contacts with key stakeholders and define common positions to present RTOs' capacities to support EU policies and needs in the field of Security & Defence.</p>
<p>European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association²³</p>	<p>EACTDA is a public-private partnership established as a non-profit organisation. It brings together European law enforcement agencies, ministries of interior, forensic institutes, and other public security practitioners, alongside relevant research and technology organisations and industry partners. The Association aims to contribute to a safer Europe by facilitating the uptake of innovative solutions by public entities across the EU and Schengen Area engaged in the fight against cybercrime. Its focus is on providing targeted end-users with a wide range of fully tested, operational-ready tools, offered free of licence costs and with access to their source code.</p>
<p>European Cybercrime Training and Education Group²⁴</p>	<p>ECTEG is an International Non-Profit Association (AISBL), composed of European Union and European Economic Area Member States law enforcement agencies, international bodies, academia, private industry and experts. Its duties include, among others, supporting harmonisation of cybercrime training across international borders, sharing knowledge, expertise and finding training solutions, and providing training and education material and reference trainers to international partners.</p>
<p>European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services²⁵</p>	<p>ENLETS promotes the use of modern technology within the law enforcement community through thematic groups focused on operational excellence. ENLETS was founded as a subgroup of the Law Enforcement Working Party (LEWP) reporting to the Standing Committee of Operational Coordination and Internal Security (COSI). The ambition was to establish a stronger connection between law enforcement agencies and innovative technologies.</p>

²¹<https://www.asd-europe.org/>

²²<https://www.earto.eu/working-group-public/wg-security-research/>

²³<https://www.eactda.eu/>

²⁴<https://www.ecteg.eu/>

²⁵<https://enlets.eu/>

Participate

Entities of different kinds participate in the programme, executing projects and disseminating results. According to the information available at the Horizon Dashboard, among the FCT R&I grant beneficiaries, we can find public bodies, private for-profit organisations, research organisations, higher or secondary education establishments and others. The share of their participation in FCT calls under the Horizon Europe programme is shown in the figure below.²⁶

Figure 3: FCT Grant Beneficiaries in Horizon Europe Calls

As far as country participation is concerned, the ENACT project is publishing a set of **Country Profile** reports that present the main entities participating in FCT projects during Horizon Europe for the top ten most active Member States and Associated Countries.²⁷

Among the projects funded under the Security Research Work Programme, the **Knowledge Networks** stand out as providing valuable resources to the entities involved in FCT R&I. During the past years, the Commission has funded several networks through the EU-funded security research Work Programme. Among the many that were launched under H2020 and Horizon Europe, two remain active that are linked to FCT. The role of these networks is to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and exploit the existing knowledge to facilitate access to subject matter knowledge to the FCT community, including policymakers, security authorities, industry, researchers and citizens. The networks also interact with security experts, organisations, projects or initiatives, those facilitating the networking among all stakeholders.

²⁶Source Horizon Dashboard, 1/04/2027, for FCT calls from 2021 to 2024

²⁷<https://enact-eu.net/results/>

Entity	Description
<p>CYCLOPES²⁸</p>	Aims to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of European law enforcement agencies combating cybercrime. The network - in addition to identifying capability gaps and requirements and sharing best practices - focuses on the ongoing dialogue with industry and academia who are delivering products and conducting research on solutions that help fight cybercrime.
<p>ENACT²⁹</p>	It is a European network to support the exchange of research and innovation knowledge as well as to increase the visibility and uptake of solutions in the fight against crime and terrorism. The network builds on four pillars, namely Networking, Research, Communication/Dissemination and Cooperation, to provide a portfolio of services to the community that range from targeted reports to validation facilities to innovation prizes and workshops and events to facilitate the visibility of the demand and the offer of innovative technology solutions for FCT.

To have a clearer picture of the entities that participate in EU-funded R&I, or even of entities which do not participate but are relevant to the FCT R&I ecosystem, the ENACT project offers invaluable resources, including the ENACT Stakeholder Map,³⁰ which is an interactive dashboard developed by the ENACT project, containing over 1,000 entities classified by the EU Security Market Taxonomy to enhance visibility and cooperation.

Figure 4 - ENACT Stakeholder Map

Updated every six months, the ENACT Stakeholder Map provides an external tool for identifying and exploring key stakeholders with relevant expertise. It functions not only as a qualified entity finder but also as a source of analytical insights. In addition, it offers an interactive environment where technology developers and providers can increase their visibility within the FCT community, thereby enhancing opportunities for innovation uptake.

²⁸<https://www.cyclopes-project.eu/>

²⁹<https://enact-eu.net/>

³⁰<https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

Key Networking Events

Several events take place periodically, providing opportunities for those interested in EU-funded FCT R&I to obtain first-hand information and liaise with key stakeholders within the ecosystem. These networking opportunities represent a valuable source of knowledge and an ideal setting to understand who's who and stay up to date with developments in the FCT R&I landscape.

Some of the most relevant include:

CERIS events:³¹ The CERIS community organises thematic workshops throughout the year, focusing on specific security domains, including Fighting Crime and Terrorism.

The screenshot displays the 'CERIS events' page. On the left, there are filter options for 'Status' (set to 'Upcoming and ongoing'), 'Event date', and 'Subject'. A 'Search' button and 'Clear filters' link are also present. The main content area shows 'CERIS events (5)' with 'Showing results 1 to 5'. An RSS icon is visible in the top right. The list of events includes:

- 19-21 MAY 2026**: Conferences and summits, [International Conference CBRNe Research & Innovation](#), France, External event.
- 05-06 MAY 2026**: Training and workshops, [Research and innovation against illicit drugs: from foresight to operational impact](#), Belgium.
- 28 APR 2026**: Training and workshops, [CERIS Workshop on innovative approaches to combating the trafficking of goods](#).
- 23-24 APR 2026**: Info days, [Security Mission Information & Innovation Group Event 2026](#), France, External event.
- 13 APR 2026**: Training and workshops, [CERIS webinar on Community Policing](#), Online only, Live streaming available.

Figure 5: CERIS Event Finder

³¹https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/ceris-events_en

Europol events:³² Europol organises specialised technical sessions and innovation-focused conferences relevant to the FCT community. Among the most impactful and widely accessible are the Europol Industry and Research Days,³³ the EC3 Cyber Innovation Forum,³⁴ and the Europol Cybercrime Conference.³⁵

Figure 6: Europol Events

eu-LISA events: The Agency organises a number of conferences throughout the year, bringing together key stakeholders in areas related to technology and innovation for large-scale information systems in the security domain. Key events include the eu-LISA High-Level Conference³⁶ and the eu-LISA Industry Roundtable.³⁷

Figure 7: eu-LISA Industry Roundtable, 2026

³²<https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/events>

³³<https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/events/europol-industry-and-research-days-2026>

³⁴<https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/events/ec3-cyber-innovation-forum-2025>

³⁵<https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/events/europols-cybercrime-annual-conference-2025>

³⁶<https://www.eulisa.europa.eu/news-and-events/events/eu-lisa-conference-2025>

³⁷<https://www.eulisa.europa.eu/news-and-events/events/eu-lisa-industry-roundtable-sep-2026>

SMI2G:³⁸ The Security Mission Information & Innovation Group (SMI2G) organises an annual two-day event to discuss upcoming Secure Societies calls under Horizon Europe. This brokerage event provides a valuable networking platform to stimulate innovative ideas and facilitate the formation of consortia. It features high-level keynote speakers, expert panel discussions, and pitch sessions related to the respective calls within Cluster 3 (Civil Security for Society).

As a result, the event offers significant networking opportunities, supporting consortium-building efforts and the exchange of valuable information on Horizon Europe security calls. Furthermore, it provides a platform for projects and networks to present their work and results in a marketplace setting. Overall, the SMI2G event represents an important opportunity to disseminate results and gather feedback from a wider community.

Figure 8: SMI2G Event, 2026

CL3 Info Day: Organised annually by the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs, the European Research Executive Agency, and the SEREN5 project, this event provides an overview of the Horizon Europe Cluster 3 calls for proposals. It covers key areas such as disaster-resilient societies, the fight against crime and terrorism, border management, cybersecurity, and infrastructure protection. Participants benefit from practical guidance on how to apply, as well as opportunities to network and build consortia for future project proposals.

³⁸<https://www.cmine.eu/events/199747>

To explore additional networking opportunities, the **ENACT Events Calendar**³⁹ provides a detailed schedule of FCT R&I-related workshops, Security Innovation Awards (SIA), and demonstration events.

The screenshot displays the ENACT website's 'Upcoming Events' section. At the top, the ENACT logo is on the left, and navigation links for 'About', 'Latest News', 'Events', 'Get Involved', 'Results', and 'SKB' are on the right. Below the navigation is a grey box with text: 'A key activity for ENACT is attendance at and organization of events dedicated to the FCT R&I community. See the sections below for information about relevant upcoming events, plans for the 2024 edition of the ENACT Annual Event, and updates from recent events we've attended.' Below this is a link: 'Think ENACT could contribute to your event? Reach out to us at enact@shu.ac.uk'.

The main content area is titled 'Upcoming Events' and features a grid of four event cards. Each card includes a header image, the event name, dates, time, and location. Below the grid is a pagination bar with numbers 1 through 7 and a right arrow.

Event Name	Dates	Time	Location
CYBERUK 2026	21 April 2026 - 23 April 2026	All Day	Glasgow
CYCLOPES Final Event	21 April 2026 - 22 April 2026	All Day	Malta
DISMANTLE Final Conference: Enhancing Police Response to Discrimination, Racism and Intolerance	22 April 2026	09:00 - 16:00	Athens, Greece
IWBF - 14th International Workshop on Biometrics and Forensics	23 April 2026 - 24 April 2026	All Day	Côte d'Azur

Figure 9: ENACT FCT Events Calendar

³⁹<https://enact-eu.net/events/>

Conclusions

The EU-funded Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT) research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem is a complex yet highly structured environment that relies on **cross-sectoral cooperation**. By pooling the resources and expertise of policymakers, law enforcement agencies, academia, and industry, the EU fosters the development of advanced civil security capabilities that could not be achieved through individual actions alone.

Navigating this landscape requires an understanding of the **diverse roles played by its stakeholders**:

Strategic steering: The European Commission (DG HOME) and Member State committees define priorities and set the strategic direction of the Work Programmes.

Operational insight: EU agencies such as Europol, eu-LISA, and CEPOL translate real-world operational experience into research priorities.

Expert advice: Informal consultative bodies, including CERIS and various industry and technology associations, provide the subject-matter expertise essential for programming and implementation.

Active participation: A wide range of beneficiaries implement projects and bring innovative solutions to operational maturity.

To maximise the impact of these efforts and avoid duplication, resources provided by networks such as **ENACT**, together with regular engagement in relevant events, play a key role.

ENACT.

European Network Against
Crime and Terrorism

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enact-eu.net

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